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Money Crisis: The Cry of Pre-service Teachers in Handling Finances

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Abstract

The purpose of this study was to determine the financial experiences of pre-service teachers in handling finances. The study used a qualitative design and focused on fourth-year BEED students at Holy Trinity College in General Santos City, Philippines. Ten participants were chosen by random sampling, and data were collected using a semi-structured interview guide. The data were then analyzed thematically. The study emphasized that pre-service teachers experiences in handling their finances are categorized into three major themes: Adjusted Habits, Proper Budgeting, and Part-Time Jobs. Pre-service teachers prepared for the future by prioritizing essentials and changing their habits. Pre-service teachers are generally known for their frugality and good financial management because it means overcoming the need to purchase the things you like, maintaining financial self-discipline can be difficult. Due to a lack of resources, teachers must be more imaginative and innovative in order to provide students with helpful instructional resources and alternative methods for delivering lessons that are effective. According to the recommendations, pre-service teachers have to get guidance and assistance with money management. Additionally, by training future pre-teachers and sharing their own experiences, experienced teachers should help pre-service and future educators.

Keywords: *financial management, part-time jobs, pre-service teachers, proper budgeting, teacher education*

Introduction

In the spur of a changing economy, knowing how to handle money is really important for everyone. This is especially true for pre-service teachers who are about to start their careers. They are at an important point, moving from being students to working, and they have their own money challenges. The phrase "money crisis" sums up the difficulties and uncertainties they go through when it comes to money during this time.

Moreover, It is really important to know about the money problems pre-service teachers face. How they handle their money can really affect how well they do in school and in their pre-service training. If we help them with these money challenges, they can become better teachers in the future. Plus, giving them advice on money can help them feel better overall and be more focused on their studies and teaching. The study of Imelda et al. (2017) showed that both experienced teachers and those pre-service teachers have very limited knowledge about basic and advanced financial concepts.

Therefore, recognizing the financial difficulties faced by pre-service teachers is extremely important. How they manage their money can greatly impact how well they do in school and grow as professionals. By addressing these issues, we can offer better support to these upcoming educators as they strive to become capable and self-assured teachers. Offering help and advice on financial matters can improve their overall happiness and mental well-being, allowing them to concentrate more on their studies and teaching duties.

In fact, the financial education and support for pre-service teachers is underscored by legal frameworks and educational policies. The Republic Act No. 10922, also known as the "Economic and Financial Literacy Act" emphasizes the need for financial education and inclusion within the educational system. Furthermore, the Department of Education Order No. 22, Series of 2021 which aims to integrate Financial Education into school curriculum and activities, providing both learners and school staff, including teachers and non-teaching personnel, with the knowledge and skills needed to make wise financial choices. This includes offering training and development opportunities for all personnel involved in education.

This study aims to accomplish several key objectives. Firstly, it aims to examine how pre-service teachers handle their finances. Secondly, it seeks to understand how these financial experiences might impact the way they teach. According to Bernz (2021), the pre-service teachers determined how they applied creative teaching as a crucial ability required to work through an obstacle in their practice. Developing a new resource to demonstrate a concept, modifying the teaching strategy to help students comprehend the learning outcome, and developing a learning experience that improves student engagement were among the issues, also taking control of your spending and making sure all of your expenses are covered on time are the fundamentals of financial discipline. Lastly, the study aims to offer valuable insights and suggestions to help overcome the financial difficulties that pre-service teachers in the Bachelor of Elementary Education program might encounter.

By conducting this study, the importance of addressing the financial literacy and stability of pre-service teachers is highlighted, ensuring they are well-prepared to enter the profession and positively influence their future students.

Research Questions

This study aimed to understand how pre-service teachers manage their finances. It answers to the following questions:

1. What are the experiences of pre-service teachers in handling their finances?
2. How these experiences affect their instructions?

Literature Review

Theoretical Lens

Our study is anchored to Financial Stress Theory by Sheldon Cohen and Thomas A. Wills (1985). It is a concept that explains how stress related to money can impact a person well-being. It suggests that it is not only about the practical aspects of money but also about the emotional toll financial challenges can take. In essence, the theory highlights that when people experience stress due to money issues, it goes beyond the surface and affects their feelings and overall mental health.

In our study, we are looking at the money crisis and the challenges pre-service teachers face with their finances. This theory helps us look beyond how financial stress affects how teachers feel. It is like a tool that lets us understand the emotions behind their money struggles, connecting the feelings to their finances. In simple terms, it helps us get the full picture of how money problems impact the well-being of pre-service teachers.

Methodology

Research Design

In this study we explored the financial experiences of pre-service teachers on their teaching practices, especially fourth-year students of college in the Bachelor of Elementary Education (BEED). Through interviews and surveys, it seeks to understand their financial challenges and how they manage their finances. The research takes place at Holy Trinity College, ensuring diverse representation and prioritizing participants well-being and confidentiality. Using a systematic approach, it was to carefully design methods, formulate appropriate questions, select participants, and analyze data. The findings will be transparent, openly addressing potential limitations and offering a comprehensive investigation into the financial management of pre-service teachers.

Participants

The participants in this study will be the pre-service teachers facing challenges in handling finances. Pre-service teachers fourth-year BEED are students of Holy Trinity College that are having difficulties on money. Pre-service teachers poverty, in which they budgeted their allowances in terms of materials, equipment, food, and transportation. We will purposely select ten (10) participants out of all pre-service teachers to be part of the study. We have deliberately chosen a group of ten participants for our qualitative research. This number enables us to thoroughly investigate the financial struggles these students face. Moreover, the criteria for selecting process of this study include fourth year pre-service teachers currently enrolled in Holy Trinity College of General Santos City for the school year 2023 - 2024, pre-service BEED teachers handling their finances from budgeting, savings and navigating the financial difficulties specific to teachers preparation. Ensuring a detailed exploration of their experiences while maintaining focus and manageability in our study.

Instruments

In this study, the researchers will take on the role of outsiders, as we will not be part of the group or community being studied. We will introduce the objectives of our study to our participants. Our study will focus on the experiences of pre-service teachers in handling finances. Moreover, we will ask for verbal permission to ensure they are comfortable sharing their experiences. A mobile phone will be utilized as a tool to record their answers during the interviews, with the aim of presenting fair and reliable information. Since this is very sensitive topic it is important to protect the identity of our participants. Therefore, we will not include their real names for their protection.

Moreover, we will stay neutral, meaning we would not have any opinions that could affect the results. Our questions during interviews will be open-ended, so participants can share what they really think. All the information we collect will be kept private and secure. When we look at the answers, we will do it in an organized way, focusing on common themes. Our goal is to share a truthful picture of how pre-service teachers handle money, helping everyone understand their challenges better and figuring out how to support them.

Procedure

In order to obtain information for this study, we will use interviews as a data collection approach. The researchers will politely approach the participants and request them to participate in an interview once the dean has approved the request letter. During the interviews, voice recording devices will be utilized to record the participants responses to obtain insightful knowledge about the pre-service teachers strategies for responding to financial difficulties encountered during their training. After the interviews, transcription of the audio recordings will be undertaken. In addition to conducting interviews, data will also be acquired through documentation and audio or voice recordings in order to ensure the collection of accurate information and enhance the studies general accuracy. Furthermore, a comprehensive analysis and transcription of the audio recordings will be conducted.

We will employ purposive sampling to select participants for this study. Purposive sampling is a type of non-random sampling method where individuals are chosen based on specific criteria (Palinkas et al., 2015). In this case, ten (10) out of the fourth year BEED pre-

service teacher in handling finances will be chosen as participants.

Moreover, the criteria for selecting process of this study include fourth year pre-service teachers currently enrolled in Holy Trinity College of General Santos City for the school year 2023 - 2024, pre-service BEd teachers handling their finances from budgeting, savings and navigating the financial difficulties specific to teachers preparation.

Ethical Considerations

We ensured that all ethical considerations were followed as mandated by the Holy Trinity College because it helped us avoid engaging in practices which may implicitly or explicitly abuse or exploit those whom we sought to do research with.

Getting the participants informed consent take priority before the study is started. We go over the benefits and significance of research participants participation in detail with them. Respondents possess the choice to include or remove specific details from their responses. We ensure that participant responses are secure and kept private.

To guarantee that the data privacy regarding participation is private and confidential, we stick to the Data Processing Agreement requirements regarding confidentiality and privacy. Additionally, we guarantee the safety of every study participant. Regardless of their ethnicity or gender, they are treated equally. Respect also be shown and practiced in order to protect participant responses and prevent manipulation. During the interview process for this study, bias or discrimination not taken into account.

Only willing participants who consent and complete the interview guide be included in this study, which concentrates on voluntary participation. This guarantees that participants are at ease and comfortable providing their opinions and insights in relation to the provided questions.

Regardless of gender (male or female), we make sure that all participants feel comfortable responding to interview questions to ensure gender sensitivity. The interests, choices, and abilities of the participants are taken into consideration through the application of methodologies and procedures. The questions that were be asked of each participant were uniform and standardized to prevent bias.

Maintaining each of the previously mentioned ethical principles, each researcher equally committed to and respectful of the educational institution.

Results and Discussion

This section presented the analyzed and interpreted data. It includes the major themes, core ideas, and frequency of responses of Pre-Service Teachers in their experiences in handling finances, presented in tabular form. Additionally, it addresses specific issues discussed in the previous chapter.

Experiences of Pre-Service Teachers in Handling their Finances

Pre-Service Teachers encountered various situations and difficulties in managing their finances, which subsequently impacted their teaching, particularly during their deployment. They found it challenging to balance their limited allowances with expenses, leading to increased stress and affecting their focus in the classroom. Some mentioned that financial constraints forced them to compromise on essential teaching materials, impacting the quality of their instruction. The pressure of managing finances also led to diminished enthusiasm, as they felt overwhelmed by the responsibilities of teaching and making ends meet.

Table 1. *Experiences of Pre-Service Teachers in Handling their Finances*

<i>Major Themes</i>	<i>Core Ideas</i>	<i>Frequency</i>
Adjusted Habits	Bringing Own Food	Typical
	Avoiding hanging out with friends	Typical
	Borrowing materials (TV, Printer, Module)	Typical
Proper Budgeting	Sorting Finances	Typical
	Making List of Expenses	Typical
Part-time Jobs	Tutoring Young Students	Typical
	Charging for Printing Services	Variant
	Watching Over a Computer Shop	Variant

Effects of Experiences on Instructions

The experiences of pre-service teachers significantly impact their instructional practices, particularly concerning financial management. Challenges faced during deployment highlight the importance of effective budgeting and resource allocation. These experiences underscore the need for comprehensive support in financial literacy to enhance teaching effectiveness. Furthermore, equipping pre-service teachers with practical financial skills can empower them to know the complexities of financing and make informed decisions for optimal classroom outcomes. Integrating financial literacy into teacher training programs can ultimately contribute to a more sustainable and efficient educational system.

Table 2. *Effects of Experiences on Instructions*

<i>Major Themes</i>	<i>Core Ideas</i>	<i>Frequency</i>
Creative	Making DIY (Do It Yourself) Materials	Typical
	Recycling Materials	Typical
Being Frugal	Learning How to Manage Budgeting Skills	Typical
	Positive Mindset in Terms of Finances	Typical
Time management	Teaching Preparation	Typical
	Doing Part-time Jobs	Typical

Conclusions

The researchers recommended that the Pre-service teachers should receive the training and support in financial management as part of their teacher preparation programs. This can include workshops, courses or resources that focus on budgeting, saving and making informed final decisions.

Furthermore, by expanding on the results of this study, future researchers can create targeted measures or instructional plans that enhance pre-service teachers understanding of finances and management abilities.

Table 1 shows the three major themes that emerged: Adjusted Habits, Proper Budgeting and Part-time Jobs. Under Adjusted Habits three core ideas were identified: Bringing own food, Avoiding hanging out with friends and Borrowing materials (TV, printer, module). In Proper Budgeting, two core ideas were highlighted: Sorting money, Making list of expenses. In Part-time Jobs three core ideas were emphasized: Tutoring Your Students, Charging for Printing Services and Watching over a computer shop.

Adjusted Habits aligns with the concept of adjusting spending, as mentioned by Suvittawat (2023), as a way for low-income earners to cope during difficult times. Essentially, both emphasize the importance of being strategic and mindful about spending money based on necessities when facing financial constraint. Through their experiences, pre-service teachers learn the value of planning ahead and making conscious decisions to achieve their financial goals.

Proper Budgeting is supported by Ramesh et al. (2019), who suggested that upon graduation, pre-service teachers would receive higher salaries than their current allowances. However, if they fail to manage this increase effectively, it could lead to financial difficulties. Hence, possessing financial literacy is crucial for addressing such money-related issues.

While Part-time Jobs, According to Ngan (2021), 70% of the benefits and reasons for part time jobs are to make money to pay for life. Therefore, a part-time job to raise money to cover life was the first reason. This aligns with the experiences shared by the pre-service teachers, where part-time jobs serve as a means to supplement their regular allowance and afford necessary teaching materials.

Table 2 shows the three major themes that emerged as effects of experiences to instructions: Creative, Develop Self Discipline and Feeling of Tension. Creative had two (2) core ideas which are making DIY (Do it yourself) materials and Recycling materials. Being Frugal included four (2) core ideas which are Learning How To Manage Budgeting Skills, and Positive mindset in terms of finances for a pre-service teacher. Time management had two (2) core ideas which are Teaching Preparation and Doing Part-time Jobs. Experienced teachers should support pre-service and future teachers by sharing their own experiences and providing mentorship. Encouraging open discussions about financial challenges and strategies for overcoming them can create a supportive community where teachers feel empowered to take control of their financial future.

Creative. Pre-service teachers are using their creativity and resourcefulness to create their own teaching materials due to limited funds for instructional supplies. By making visual aids, worksheets, and props from everyday items, they can engage their students effectively without spending extra money. These experiences are teaching them the value of ingenuity and adaptability, skills that will benefit them throughout their teaching careers. Despite financial constraints, these teachers are providing quality instruction and showcasing their talents, demonstrating resilience and determination to succeed. Jp (2021) states that the pre-service teachers determined how they used creative teaching as a critical skill needed to overcome a challenge in their practice.

Time Management. Pre-service teachers often facetime and financial challenges, balancing many responsibilities with limited allowances. To save money, they make their own teaching materials, take on part-time jobs, and prepare for teaching duties. They manage their time carefully to juggle these tasks effectively, striving to provide quality instruction despite these demands. Organizing their time efficiently is crucial for success, allowing them to fulfill teaching responsibilities while handling other commitments. Despite these challenges, they remain determined to deliver impactful teaching experiences through careful planning and perseverance. According to Olivo (2021), one of the most crucial aspects of classroom management is time management. Teachers' concentration improves when they master time management skills.

There are three generated themes of the experience of a Pre-service teacher when it comes to handling their finances; Adjusted Habits, Proper Budgeting and Part Time Jobs. According to Ramesh, et. al study, pre-service teachers will start getting a higher salary than what they get as an allowance now. Also, knowing about financial stuff would help these new teachers deal with money issues.

Additionally, to manage proper budgeting, the core ideas of these are that pre-service teachers have valuable experience that helps them

in proper budgeting, adjusting habits, and doing part time jobs. They had a positive outcome by viewing these challenges, and their struggles now serves as an eye-opener for them. Regarding their Challenging Experiences, the core idea is that pre-service teachers struggle and experience difficulty in handling finances.

Also, regarding their experiences in Handling Finances in terms of effect on instructions, there are two generated themes; Creative, Developed Financial Discipline and Challenging Effects. The core idea belonging to creativity is that pre-service teachers have creative skills and innovation in terms of their instructional materials and it needs a lot of time. Flexibility of using materials due to the insufficient materials stated in the core ideas of the table.

On the other hand, when it comes to how those experiences affect their motivation for instructional materials, there are three generations themes, Creative, Developed Financial Discipline and Challenging Effects. When it comes to insufficient materials also result in pre-service teachers being stressed and experiencing struggles when it comes to instructional materials.

As a result, they gain a deeper understanding of how to handle finances through experiences in their instructional materials. The pre-service teachers expect to be more knowledgeable about finances. Developing knowledge about finances can benefit pre-service teachers in various ways. It can help them manage their instructional materials more effectively by making informed decisions about resource allocation. Regarding insufficient materials, being creative and innovative is crucial when coping with insufficient materials. Teachers can explore alternative ways to present information, such as using digital resources, incorporating interactive activities, or encouraging students to create their own learning materials. This approach not only helps overcome resource limitations but also enhances the learning experience for students by making it more engaging and interactive.

Pre-service teachers often face challenges in managing their finances, especially as they juggle various obligations. They felt tension because of the responsibilities they had to do before going to their respective school where they are employed. It is important for them to experience those challenges to become more knowledgeable about financial management to effectively meet their financial responsibilities. This includes budgeting, prioritizing expenses, and finding ways to save money, which are essential skills for navigating the financial demands of being a pre-service teacher. The pre-service teacher needed more motivation.

Despite facing challenges in managing their finances, pre-service teachers continue to adapt and adjust their instructional materials. With the support of their families and their mentor, they remain motivated to find creative solutions to both financial challenges and instructional needs despite the difficulties they have experienced.

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